

Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Tetramethylthiuram Disulphide by Extraction of its Chromium Complex into Isobutyl Methyl Ketone

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WE present here a more sensitive method for the determination of tetramethylthiuram disulphide (thiram) after extracting its chromium complex into isobutyl methyl ketone.

Experimental

A digital pH meter and a Spectronic SP-20 spectrophotometer were used. Thiram (Wilson Laboratories Bombay) was recrystallised from alcohol and its purity was checked by elemental analysis and m.p. (150°) which were in agreement with the values in the literature. A 0.1% solution of thiram was prepared in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, the solution was boiled, cooled, filtered and standardised¹; further dilutions were carried out with distilled water as required. A 0.5% solution of chromium acetate² in distilled water was prepared. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: To a known volume (≤ 1 ml) of sample containing upto 50 μg of thiram, were added 0.5% chromium acetate (2 ml) and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (2 ml; pH=2.5) and the solution was diluted to 5 ml with distilled water. This solution was shaken with an equal volume (5 ml) of methyl isobutyl ketone for 1 min. The organic phase was then dried in fused calcium chloride. A second extraction was carried out similarly and the organic phase gave negligible absorbance. So the absorbance of the first extract was measured at 420 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance of the extract remains constant in the pH range 2.0–3.5 and when 1.5–2.0 ml of 0.5% chromium acetate solution was used. The complex was not extractable into benzene, carbon tetrachloride, toluene and hexane but could be extracted with amyl acetate, chloroform, butane-2-one, ethyl acetate, isobutanol and isobutyl methyl ketone. Maximum absorbance was observed with isobutyl methyl ketone and hence it was used in this method. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for 40 min.

A calibration curve was constructed under optimum conditions described above. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 5–80 μg per 5 ml of the final solution. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity (for an absorbance of 0.001) were calculated to be $0.864 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0277 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 420 nm. Ten replicate determinations containing 50 μg of thiram gave mean absorbance of 0.36 with a relative standard deviation of 0.41%.

Composition of chromium-thiram complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method and the stoichiometry was found to be 2:3. Thus the extraction of $\text{Cr}_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}_4]_3$ complex is suggested under these conditions.

Effect of diverse ions: Sample solutions containing upto 50 μg of thiram and various amounts of different metal ions were prepared and thiram was determined by general procedure in the presence of various ions. The following foreign ions (mg amount in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of thiram 50 μg in 5 ml of final solution: Pb^{II} (1.251), Zn^{II} (0.500), Cd^{II} (0.870), Fe^{III} (0.6892) and Mn^{II} (0.649). Cu^{II} interfered strongly. Bromide(26), iodide(30), chloride(9.75), nitrate(24), citrate(36), sulphate(27) did not interfere but EDTA, thiosulphate and metabisulphite interfered strongly. Different amines also interfered.

Synthetic mixtures of disodium ethylene bisdithiocarbamate (nabam), zinc dimethyldithiocarbamate (ziram), sodium monomethyldithiocarbamate (vapam), tetramethylthiuram disulphide (thiram) and sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate in various proportions were prepared. Taking advantage of the solubility difference, ziram and thiram were extracted into chloroform while nabam, vapam and sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate remained in the aqueous phase. Then chloroform was evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide; ziram being soluble in cold could be separated while thiram dissolved only on boiling and was determined by the general procedure.

Applications: The applicability of the method was tested by analysis of a variety of mixtures containing upto 80 μg of thiram in the aliquot. The method is selective for the determination of thiram in the presence of nabam, vapam and sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate. It is one of the most sensitive methods available for thiram determination and could be used in the analysis of commercial samples and good recoveries were obtained from food-stuffs (95–95.5%). Table 1 shows typical results of five dilutions of stock solutions prepared from two commercial samples, Thiram 100% (Wilson Laboratories) and Thiram 75% (Swarup Chemicals P. Ltd.). Results obtained by the method of Fischer¹ are also shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF COMMERCIAL SAMPLES OF THIRAM

Sample wt %	% Thiram present	% Thiram found		Relative standard deviation	Accuracy %
		Proposed method	Fischer method		
Thiram (100)	0.100	0.099	0.096	0.71	1.00
	0.200	0.198	0.198	0.35	1.00
	0.400	0.399	0.398	0.75	0.25
	0.600	0.597	0.596	0.26	0.50
	0.800	0.799	0.798	0.09	0.13
Thiram (75)	0.100	0.0987	0.097	0.58	1.33
	0.200	0.1986	0.196	0.29	0.70
	0.400	0.3980	0.398	0.14	0.50
	0.600	0.5960	0.597	0.09	0.66
	0.800	0.7990	0.798	0.07	0.13

Comparison of sensitivity: According to Lowen³, Cullen⁴ and Verma⁵ minimum of 15.9, 31.8 and 25 μg of thiram equivalent to 10, 20 and 15.72 μg of CS_2 evolved can be determined respectively, but according to the present method 5 μg of thiram equivalent to 3.144 μg of CS_2 can be determined. Moreover, this method is simple direct and less time-consuming.

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References

1. W. FISCHER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 137, 90.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed. Longman, London, 1978, p. 738.
3. W. K. LOWEN, *J. Assoc. Off. Agric. Chem.*, 1953, 36, 484.
4. T. E. CULLEN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 36, 221.
5. N. VERMA, Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, 1985.

Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of some Sulpha Drugs using Acetylacetone as a Coupling Agent

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SULPHA drugs have been separated by various chromatographic procedures, e.g. paper chromatography¹ and thin layer chromatography². Poethke and Kize³ employed two-dimensional tlc on alumina plates but all the sulpha drugs investigated could not be separated. Wehrh⁴ reported the separation of sulpha drugs using *N*-(1-naphthyl)-

ethylenediammonium dichloride as a coupling agent. Sulpha drugs in amounts upto 4 μg have been quantitatively estimated by Wagner and Wandel⁵ using chloroform-n-butanol-light petroleum (1:1:10, v/v). Twenty sulphonamides were separated on thin layers of ion-exchangers in different solvent systems⁶. Various new chromogenic reagents for the detection of sulphonamides on tlc plates have been reported⁷. Srivastava *et al.*⁸ separated ten closely related sulpha drugs on silica gel impregnated with cadmium acetate.

The present paper describes the resolution and identification of some sulpha drugs in the form of their acetylacetone derivatives. Thus a mixture of sulpha drugs was converted into the coupled products on thin-layer plates and subsequently chromatographed. In a mixture of nine sulpha drugs it was possible to characterise 0.1–0.2 μg of each drug in the form of its coupled product.

Experimental

All the solvents used were freshly dried and distilled. Tlc-glass plates (20×20 cm) for supporting the layer were used. An ascending irrigation technique was employed.

Preparation of coupled products: A sulpha drug (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol, 0.69 g) was added to it and the resulting diazonium salt was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (10.0 g) and acetylacetone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The solid product was then washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals: sulphaphenazole, m.p. 205°; sulphamethiazole, 225°; sulphadimidine, 190°; sulphamethoxazole, 175°; sulphathiazole, 155°; sulphacetamide, 155°; metacalfin, 130°; phthalylsulphathiazole, 210°; sulphasomidine, 180°.

Adsorbents: The following adsorbents were employed: A, silica gel-G (E. Merck, throughout); B, silica gel-G with 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide; C, silica gel-G with 1% Triton-X 100; D, silica gel-G with 1% sodium lauryl sulphate; E, silica gel-G with 1% cupric acetate; F, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 ; G, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide; H, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% Triton-X 100; I, silica gel-G with 20% CaCO_3 and 1% sodium lauryl sulphate.

Procedure: Tlc plates (0.5 mm thickness) of the above mentioned adsorbents were prepared and spotted with the solutions of coupled products of sulpha drugs in acetone. After air-drying these plates at room temperature, they were irrigated with suitable solvents. It took about 30 min to run the solvent system 16 cm. Yellow or orange spots could be observed without any visualising agent. However, for dilute solutions (below 0.1 μg) the spots could be visualised